

**AN APPLICATION
OF THE
KAUFMANN AND GIL ALUJA FUZZY CHAINS
TO MANAGEMENT CONTROL.
FUZZY CASH MANAGEMENT**

by

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"En lugar de una teoría económica enue otral mucbu queexiateo. propood remos uq trabajo mucho más modesto: emplear de la mejor manera posible las Informaciottes disponibles para construir modelos matemáticos intentando engañarnos lo menos posible... a nosotros mismos".

A. Kaufmann and J. Gil Aluja

(Técnicas operativas de gestión para el tratamiento de la Incertidumbre, 1987)

I. Introduction

One of the important questions in management control is decision making that affects the cash-flows and, at the end, the financial outcomes of one firm. At least, three problems are stated: first, do not maintain idle balance of liquidity, that is to say, producing a profitability under a better choice; second, do not finance overdrafts paying higher taxes than better ones; and third, avoid that, at the same time, credits are used with higher rates of interests and there exists an excess of resources at lower rates.

Figure 1 illustrates a typical cash management system. Positive and negative cash flows can take place daily. As far as the first, is concerned, (hey can serve as a cover for the second when these are produced, but there may exist a time period between both in which it would be absurd to maintain idle cash balances, as previously mentioned. This system has two relevant costs to be considered: (1) the opportunity costs (or the loss of revenues) to maintain cash values instead of having them in an investment portfolio and (2) the transaction cost that occurs when moving investment shares to the funds or vice versa those that are related to the commissions collected by the agent or the runner which in the end becomes a buying and selling operation.

Figure 1. Typical cash management system.

Consequently, cash management entails the resolution of two interdependent questions: fixing an optimum level of liquidity and determining the term and amount of the transfer of payments between the funds and the investment portfolios (liquid assets).

To this respect, our study will begin with the situation in which is known the exact behavior of cash flows as the first step in the sequential process of bringing us closer to other more realistic expositions. This way, the present paper is divided into two main parts. The first will study the most usual techniques for the resolution of the problems stated and the interest in the application of the Markov chains when considering the cash flow as a random variable.

Nevertheless, there are situations in which it is not possible to use probabilities, as when there is uncertainty instead of aleatoriness. If our knowledge of the environment is imprecise, as it can occur in cash management decision making, the model must include the notion of chains with fuzzy data instead of probabilities, recently developed by KAUFMANN and GIL ALUJA (1991). So, in the second part, the aim of our study is to examine the uncertain chains (normal fuzzy relations) expanded by the above named professors, as valid operative tools to evaluate the options of cash management systems.

U. Proposals for the Cash Management Control In an environment of certitude and of randomness

The most common cash management techniques are based mainly on the models of the control of inventories (stocks) and the only present significant differences with regard to the different considerations of the behavior of cash flows. On one hand models can be found for example, like those developed by BAUMOL (1952) and BERANEK (1975) which assume an environment of certitude, and on the other there are the probabilistic models, say, those of PATINKIN (1956) and MILLER and ORR (1966) - here the cash flows are considered to behave like a random variable. However, like the previous ones they are also especially interested in fixing the optimum amount of cash balance.

Nevertheless, the effects to be determined of the term and amount of the transactions between the funds and the investment portfolios can be of interest to prove the application of the Markov chains when considering the cash flow as a random variable.

D.I. Cash Management Control in an environment of certitude

One of the most known models of cash management in "perfect prevision" conditions or before certitude is the BAUMOL model (1952) according to which the cash balances evolve in the way in which Figure 2 describes. That is to say that inflow to the funds are produced instantaneously for example, one day, while the outflow are carried out regularly in the long run.

Figure 2. Profile of the evolution of cash balances according to the BAUMOL model.

Let us suppose that we are set at the moment of t_0 . According to Figure 2, the initial cash balance is T , one part of that balance, R , is retained in funds for precautionary reasons and the rest, I , is invested in liquid securities which offer financial earnings of i . In the beginning, R is sufficient to cover the payments for the period which runs from t_0 to t_1 , one week if the cycle of collections is monthly. In t_1 will be sold c monetary units of liquid securities which will be encashed in funds and will serve to cover the corresponding payments to the period between t_1 and t_2 . In the same way, c monetary units of securities will be transformed in funds in t_2 and t_3 . At the end of the cycle, that is to say in t^* , funds will be encashed in T pesetas over which will be carried out a similar assignment between investment and initial funds.

The time elapsed between t_0 and t_1 is the same as $(T - R)/T$, supposing that the disbursements observe a regular pattern throughout the length of the cycle. Moreover, the average cash balance in that period would be approximately $(T - R)/2$. The proper opportunity cost to maintain R pesetas between t_0 and t_1 could be written as $[(T - R)/2] i [(T - R)/T]$, with i expressing an annual rate and $(T - R)/T$ a fraction of a year. The transaction cost associated with the investment in stocks of I monetary units in t_0 will be the same as $a + KJ$, where a and KJ are, respectively, the fixed costs and proper variables of the operation.

On the other hand, the costs related to the cash management in the rest of the cycle can be written in the following manner:

$$\begin{array}{rcccl}
 \text{Costs} & = & (c/2) i & (1/T) & + & (b. + & V) (1/c) \\
 \text{Average cash} & & \text{Period of} & & & \text{Fixed} & \text{Variable Number of} \\
 \text{balance} & & \text{time from} & & & \text{cost} & \text{Cost operations} \\
 & & t, t_{ou} & & & & \\
 \hline
 & = & \text{Opportunity cost} & & + & \text{Transaction cost} &
 \end{array}$$

Adding the two expressions of costs corresponding to the periods $t_0 t_1$ and $t_{1,}$, we have the total costs proper to the cash management from t_0 to t_U , that is to say, the complete cycle of funds.

$$\begin{aligned}
 CT = & (T-1/2) i (T-1/T) + b_g + K_{ol} + \\
 & + (c/2) i (1/T) + (b. + K.c) / c
 \end{aligned}$$

Deriving this expression with respect to c we can obtain the optimum cash balance, that is to say, that value which makes minimum the sum of the opportunity and transaction costs.

$$\begin{aligned}
 5 \quad CT / Sc & = (i / 2T / (2T)^2) + (- b_r / c^2) = \\
 & \leftarrow 0 / 2T - b. / c^2 = 0
 \end{aligned}$$

$$c^2 - b. 12 T / i i$$

$$c = 2 \cdot b. \sqrt{i}$$

Apart from the attraction of the model, the restrictive character of the starting hypothesis makes it applicable only in a limited number of cases. In effect, most of the enterprises register inflows and outflows of funds in the long run that do not observe the regular rythm conjectured by the model, from which the hypothesis of certitude would not be admissible in a great number of cases, which grants the same reduced margin of operations.

Here it supposed that p_i do not depend on n (stationary chain). We can also represent (2) in the form of a matrix:

$$\begin{array}{c}
 \begin{array}{|c|c|} \hline E_1 & E_2 \\ \hline p_1(n+1) & p_2(n+1) \\ \hline \end{array} \quad \dots \quad \begin{array}{|c|} \hline E_h \\ \hline h(n+1) \\ \hline \end{array} = \\
 \\
 \begin{array}{|c|c|} \hline E_1 & E_2 \\ \hline p_1(n) & p_2(n) \\ \hline \end{array} \quad \dots \quad \begin{array}{|c|} \hline E_h \\ \hline p_h(n) \\ \hline \end{array} \quad 0 \\
 \\
 \begin{array}{c}
 E_i \\
 E_j \\
 \vdots \\
 E_r
 \end{array}
 \begin{array}{c}
 E_i, E_j \\
 \begin{array}{|c|c|} \hline p_{ij} & p_{ji} \\ \hline p_{in} & p_{jn} \\ \hline \vdots & \vdots \\ \hline p_{ri} & p_{ri} \\ \hline \end{array}
 \end{array}
 \begin{array}{c}
 \dots \\
 \dots \\
 \ddots \\
 \dots
 \end{array}
 \begin{array}{c}
 E_h \\
 \begin{array}{|c|} \hline p_{ih} \\ \hline p_{jh} \\ \hline \vdots \\ \hline p_{rh} \\ \hline \end{array}
 \end{array}
 \quad (3)
 \end{array}$$

where 0 signifies the composition *sum*product* (rows by columns).

It can also be written in a simplified form:

$$(P(n+1)) = [p(n)]^J * [M] \tag{4}$$

The transition matrix formed by the probabilities p_{ij} and designated by [M] will be called 'stochastic matrix' and will possess the properties to be pointed out:

$$P(n) \geq 0; \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, N \quad n = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots \tag{5}$$

$$\sum_{j \rightarrow} E_j p_j(n) = 1; \quad n = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots \tag{6}$$

$$\sum_i p_{ij} = 0; \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, N \tag{7}$$

$$\sum_i E_i p_{ij} = 1; \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, N \tag{8}$$

In particular, let us suppose that the matrix in Figure 4 describes the behavior of cash balances. The numbers of the vertical column (rows) are the amounts of money (monetary units) in the cash basis accounting in the morning of day n . The numbers of the superior row (columns) are the cash balances in monetary units (u.m.) in the morning of day $n+1$. The table shows for example, that if the cash balance is 2 (20.000 u.m.) on day n , it will be 1 (10.000 u.m.) on day $n+1$ with the probability of 0.177 (the number marked in row 2, column 1, es 0.177). In this way, Figure 4 shows the transition matrix of the process, based on the control system described in figure 3, where the figure above the datum line is superior to 5 and inferior to 1, with the point of return the same as 2. In said matrix, the rows 2, 3, and 4 show the calculations or measurements of the probability that the system moves from one state to another. To deduce the probabilities of states 1 to 5 immediately transfers to position 2, from there the data in rows 1, 5, and 2 are the same.

	1	2	3	4	5
1	.177	.588	.235	0	0
2	.177	.588	.235	0	0
3	0	.29	.184	.526	0
4	0	0	.324	.541	.135
5	.177	.588	.235	0	0

Figure 4. Transition matrix of cash balance.

The stochastic matrix of Figure 4 is the transition matrix of one pan of this problem, facilitating the knowledge of the probability of the system moving from one state to another in one step. In this way, in order to obtain the transition matrix in 2 steps it is enough to multiply one step by itself; we can generalize this in a symbolic form saying that $[M]$ is the transition matrix of one step, the transition matrix of n steps would be $(M)^n$, which signifies the product of n factors like $[M]$.

The transition matrix of n steps facilitates answering the above question for the controller, that is, it is of interest to know the probability that the system be in a specific state after n transitions. Thus, if in expression (4) we make $n \neq 0$, we obtain:

$$[p(1)]^n [p(0)]_0 [M]^n$$

In a similar way, $(p(2)) \rightarrow [p(1)]_1 [M]$ and by substitution

$$[p(2)] = (p(1))_1 [M] - (p(0))_1 [M] \circ [M] - [p(0)]_1 [M]^2$$

Therefore, expression (4) could be written as follows:

$$[p(n)J = [p(0)J \circ [M]^n \tag{9}$$

where $p(0)$ is the probability vector for finding the system in a particular state in the instant of 0, that is, when the system is inspected for the first time.

In our case of application, let us suppose that at the controller arrives on Monday morning and proves that the system is in state 3 (30.000 u.m.) and wants to know the probability of finding the system in state 1 on Wednesday morning, then he should sell shares in order to obtain money and it would be of interest to determine beforehand which investment shares should be sold.

According to expression (9), we obtain

$$[p(2)J = [p(0)J \circ [M]^2 =$$

$$= [0 \ 0 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0] \circ \begin{matrix} \begin{matrix} .135 & .518 & .223 & .124 & 0 \\ .135 & .518 & .223 & .124 & 0 \\ .051 & .224 & .272 & .381 & .071 \\ .024 & .173 & .267 & .463 & .073 \\ .135 & .518 & .223 & .124 & 0 \end{matrix} \end{matrix} =$$

$$= (.051 \ .224 \ .272 \ .381 \ .071]$$

Since the data in column 1 is 0.051, the controller knows that the probability of having to transfer funds from securities to cash is only 0.051 which does not appear to be prudent to dedicate much time in determining which shares should be sold if the necessity were to arise on Wednesday.

On the other hand, expression (9) could also be used to specify the probability of the system moving from one state to another in any number of transitions if the probabilities of one step do not change with time, which leads us to the consideration that the stationary probabilities, that is, the ergodic property in a Markov chain (KAUFMANN, 1966).

In this way, if $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} [M]^n = [M]$

where $[M]$ is a stochastic matrix with no null elements we say the system is ergodic and possesses a permanent conduct. The matrix $[M]$ which possesses this property is denominated as an *ergodic matrix*. There, is one test in two parts which states that if one of the ergodic Markov chains: (a) there should be a positive probability that it can go from one state i to any other j if there are enough transitions and (b) there should exist at least one state with the positive probability that the system remain there after a transition.

If $[M]$ is such that all of its lines are identical then it is said that the system is "completely ergodic", and in this case, for n sufficiently large, the state of the system does not depend upon the initial state. In effect

$$\begin{aligned}
 (p(n))_j &= (p(0))_j \circ [M]^n \\
 \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} (p(n)) &= [p(0)] \circ [S?] \quad (10) \\
 &= [p]
 \end{aligned}$$

where $[p]$ is one of the lines identical to $[E?]$.

To calculate the asyndotic probabilities $[p]$ there exist various methods, one of the simplest, especially if there exists the option of multiplying the matrixes included in the majority of the Electronic Spreadsheet, consist in calculating $[M]^n$ until $[M]^n = [M]$

$[M]$						$[M]$					
.177	.588	.235	0	0	o	.177	.588	.235	0	0	=
.177	.588	.235	0	0		.177	.588	.235	0	0	
0	.29	.184	.526	0		0	.29	.184	.526	0	
0	0	.324	.541	.135		0	0	.324	.541	.135	
.177	.588	.235	0	0		.177	.588	.235	0	0	

$[M]^2$				
.135	.518	.223	.124	0
.135	.518	.223	.124	0
.051	.224	.272	.381	.071
.024	.173	.267	.463	.073
.135	.518	.223	.124	0

.....

$$[M]^4 = \begin{bmatrix} .083 & .348 & .248 & .284 & .038 \\ .083 & .348 & .248 & .284 & .038 \\ .083 & .347 & .248 & .284 & .038 \\ .083 & .347 & .248 & .284 & .038 \\ .083 & .348 & .248 & .284 & .038 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$[M]^{17} = \begin{bmatrix} .083 & .347 & .248 & .284 & .038 \\ .083 & .347 & .248 & .284 & .038 \\ .083 & .347 & .248 & .284 & .038 \\ .083 & .347 & .248 & .284 & .038 \\ .083 & .347 & .248 & .284 & .038 \end{bmatrix}$$

In our case of application, we have

$$[p] = (.083 \ .347 \ .248 \ .284 \ .038)$$

We can observe that $p(1) = 0.083$ and there are 260 work days in the year, then the number of times that the system will be in state 1 in said year would be $0,083 \times 260 = 21.58$ times. Therefore, "an average" would have to move investment shares to funds some 21.58 times a year and once every $260/21,58 = 12$ days. A similar analysis for state 5 produces $0.038 \times 260 = 9.88$ movements from the funds to securities a year. This information is of great interest in planning the period and amount of transactions between the funds and investment shares.

Nevertheless, despite the attraction of the application of the Markov chains, it Js necessary to recall that in order to apply a probability, in the first place, it is necessary to have a succession of phenomenons that are repeated under determined conditions and, in the second place, can have the results obtained applied over another phenomenon subjected to the same conditions as the previous ones.

Concerning that, there are situations in which it is not possible to use probabilities, as when there is uncertainty instead of aleatoriness. If our knowledge of the environment is imprecise, as happens in cash management decision making, the model must indicate the notion of chains with fuzzy data instead of probabilities recently developed by KAUFMANN and GIL ALUJA (1991).

m. Proposal for the Cash Management Control in an Environment of Uncertainty:
Fuzzy Kaufmann and Gil Aluja Chains

In an environment of uncertainty the model must include the notion of the level of presumption, that is, instead of a law of probability there should be laws of possibility. Nevertheless, there exists a great parallelism between the theory of probabilities and possibilities: in the first, fundamental axiom is the addition of the measurement, the second, fundamental axiom is the monotony of the inclusion for all assessments.

With this respect, the KAUFMANN and GIL ALUJA (1991) proposal is based on the Markovian theory, although it presents important modifications when situated in an environment of uncertainty and consequently doesn't employ other probabilities. On the other hand, the Markov chain is carried out through associated sum-product operators while the uncertain chains are carried out through associated maximum-minimum operators.

Let us then construct the previously considered model for the problem of cash management in doubt through a "fuzzy chain by Kaufmann and Gil Aluja". For this, following said authors, let us place a system S whose joint state is $\in \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_N\}$ (N finite). It is possible that it be valued at $[0, 1]$ the possibility of S occurring can be found in the state $E_i, i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N$ and this for all $n = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots$ and designated possibilities $q_i(n), i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N, n = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots$

The $q_i(n)$ form the elements of the set of vectors of state which describe the system for all future moments to be considered.

$$[q(n)] = \begin{array}{|c|c|} \hline E_1 & E_2 \\ \hline p_1(n) & q_2(n) \\ \hline \end{array} \dots \begin{array}{|c|} \hline E_N \\ \hline q_N(n) \\ \hline \end{array} \quad (ID)$$

Established is the hypothesis that $q(n)$ form a law of possibility for all n , that is, to say that there is:

$$\begin{matrix} N \\ \forall q_i(n) \geq 1 \\ i \in I \end{matrix} \tag{12}$$

Said another way, at least one of the states has the possibility of 1.

It also parts from the hypothesis that the possibility of passing from one state E_j , to another state E_i only depends on E_i and E_j . It is supposed that the possibility of every set can be valued $(E_i, E_j, j = 1, 2, \dots, N, i, j \text{ at is } q_{ij})$ knowing that the system will be found in the state E_j in the moment $n+1$ and is m the state E_i in the moment n . Established then is the equation which guides the system;

$$q_i(n+1) = \sum_{j=1}^N q_j(n) A_{ij}(n), j = 1, 2, \dots, N \tag{13}$$

It is supposed here that q^i does not depend on n (stationary chains).

On the other hand:

$$\forall i \in \{1, 2, \dots, N\} \exists j \in \{1, 2, \dots, N\}$$

$$\begin{matrix} N \\ \forall q_i = 1 \\ i \in I \end{matrix} \tag{U}$$

In other words, every row of the relation contains at least one 1.

In this way, the q_{ij} a fuzzy normal relation which will be denominated "fuzzy matrix" compared with the "stochastic matrix". The system constructed based on the "fuzzy matrix" will be denominated "fuzzy chain" (understanding with normal rows) so as not to call, it a fuzzy Markov chain since the name Markov carries with it notions of probability.

We can present anew the expression (13) under the Matrix form:

$$\begin{array}{c}
 \begin{array}{ccc}
 E_1 & E_2 & E_N \\
 \boxed{q_1(n+1)} & \boxed{q_2(n+1)} & \dots \dots \boxed{q_N(n+1)}
 \end{array} = \\
 \\
 = \begin{array}{c}
 E_1, E_2 \\
 \boxed{q_1(n)} \quad \boxed{q_2(n)}
 \end{array} * \begin{array}{c}
 E_N \\
 \boxed{q_N(n)}
 \end{array} * \begin{array}{c}
 E_1, E_2 \\
 \boxed{q_{11}} \quad \boxed{q_{12}} \quad \dots \\
 \boxed{q_{21}} \quad \boxed{q_{22}} \quad \dots \\
 \vdots \quad \vdots \quad \ddots \\
 E_N \\
 \boxed{q_{N1}} \quad \boxed{q_{N2}} \quad \dots
 \end{array} \begin{array}{c}
 E_n \\
 \boxed{q_{1n}} \\
 \boxed{q_{2n}} \\
 \vdots \\
 \boxed{q_{Nn}}
 \end{array} \quad (15)
 \end{array}$$

where * signifies the $\rightarrow \text{max, min} \rightarrow$ composition (rows by columns) or also

$$\mu_n(x, z) = \bigvee_y (\mu_H(x, y) \wedge \mu_n(y, z)) \quad (16)$$

Given that $q_i(n)$ and q_j are values, and must fulfill that:

$$\begin{array}{l}
 q_i(n) \in [0, 1] \\
 N
 \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l}
 j = 1, 2, \dots, N \\
 n = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots
 \end{array} \quad (17)$$

$$\bigvee_{i=1}^N q_i(n) = 1, \quad n = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots \quad (18)$$

$$Q_{ij} \geq 0 \quad (19)$$

$$\bigvee_{i=1}^N q_i^*(n) = 1, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, N \quad (20)$$

Also written under the form:

$$[q(n+1)] = [q(n)] \cdot [N] \quad (21)$$

where $[N]$ is the matrix formed by the values q^* introduced in (15). In this way $[N]_J$ is a fuzzy relation of the normal rows according to the terminology of the theory of the fuzzy subsets. The premise that q depends on time and will be $\langle 7/n \rangle$ then $[N(n)]$ represents a chain called 'not stationary'.

We can broaden our consideration for educational interests that present the notion of fuzzy $\wedge$ -normal relations. A fuzzy $\wedge$ -normal relation possesses values constituted by confidence intervals:

$$f_{e, a_j} \in [0, 1] \quad 0 < a_1, a_2 < 1 \quad (22)$$

but given that the relation is normal, there will always exist at least one 1 in every row. Let us remember that:

$$(a, a] = a \quad a \in [0, 1] \quad (23)$$

$$f_{e_i} \wedge f_{e_j} (A) f_{e_i} \wedge f_{e_j} = [a_i, a_j] \wedge [a_i, a_j] \quad (24)$$

$$f_{e_i} \vee f_{e_j} (V) f_{e_i} \vee f_{e_j} = f_{e_i} \vee f_{e_j}, \quad a_i, a_j \in [0, 1] \quad (25)$$

The maxmin composition will be carried out with the confidence intervals in the same way as the values of $[0, 1]$, respecting (23), (24) and (25). The confidence intervals of $[0, 1]$ are commutative, associative, distributive, etc..., have the same algebraic properties as the values of $[0, 1]$.

In conclusion, a fuzzy $\wedge$ -normal chain can be treated in the same way as a fuzzy normal chain even if to differentiate the symbolic effects are expressed by (N_i) .

In particular, let us suppose that the matrix in Figure 5 describes the behavior estimated as the possible cash balance. The numbers of the vertical columns (rows) are the amounts of money (u.m.) in the cash accounting on the morning of day n . The numbers of the superior row (columns) are the cash balances in u.m. on the morning of day $n+1$. The table indicates that for example, if the cash balance is 2 on day n , the possibility that it be 1 on day $n+1$ is $(0.2, 0.4)$ (the number marked in row 2, column 1, is $(0.2, 0.4)$).

	1	2	3	4	5
1	(.2, .4]	1	(.3, .5]	0	0
2	(.2, .4]	1	(.3, .5]	0	0
3	0	(.4, .7]	.35	1	0
4	0	0	.6	1	(.1, .4]
5	(.2, .4]	1	(.3, .5]	0	0

Figure 5. Fuzzy $\wedge$ -normal relation of the cash balance.

In this way, Figure 5 shows the transition matrix where, as in the previous case, it is supposed that the effects of the control system of the liquid management, a grade superior to 5 and inferior to 1 where the rate of return is equal to 2. In said matrix, rows 2, 3 and 4 show values (subjective opinion) of a system that moves from one state to another. Rows 1 and 5 are deduced by a similar form as in the previous case.

This fuzzy $\wedge$ -normal relation facilitates the controller answering the question about the level of conjecture of the possibility that the system be found in a specific state in a near future moment, since when using the values it is of interest to know, from the subjective data, the results for a more elevated conjecture.

For this, in a similar way to that considered in expression (10), will be calculated $[N]_{\sim}^*$ until $([N]_{\sim}^{k+1} = [N]_{\sim}^k)$, where there is

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} [N]_{\sim}^k = [N]_{\sim}^*$$

Nevertheless, with the maxmin composition it is necessary to adopt a fuzzy $\wedge$ -normal relation limited to the transitive closure $[[N]_{\sim}]$, that is:

$$[[N]_{\sim}] = [N] \cup ([N] \circ [N]) \cup \dots \quad (26)$$

since except in the case where $[N]_{\sim}$ is reflexive it will not always be met that $[[N]_{\sim}]^* = [N]_{\sim}^*$ and the "strongest" route in the value graph is obtained considering the transitive closure.

In our case we have the application:

[N]				
.2,4	1	.3,5	0	0
.2,4	1	.3,5	0	0
0	.4,.7	.35	1	0
0	0	.6	1	.1,4
.2,4	1	.3,5	0	0

" ≤ 1				
.2,4	1	.3,5	0	0
.2,4	1	.3,5	0	0
0	.4,.7	.35	1	0
0	0	.6	1	.1,4
.2,4	1	.3,5	0	0

=
=

[[N] _~]				
(.2, .4]	1	[-3, .5]	(.3, 5)	0
[.2, .4]	1	[.3, .5]	[.3, .5]	0
[-2, .4]	(.4, .7]	.6	1	[.1, .4]
[.1, .4]	[-4, .7]	.6	1	[1, -.4]
1-2, .4]	1	[3, .5]	[.3, .5]	0

$$[\tilde{N}]^3 = \begin{array}{|c|c|c|c|c|} \hline [-2, .4] & 1 & [-3, .5] & [-3, .5] & (-1, -.4) \\ \hline [-2, .4] & 1 & [-3, .5] & [-3, .5] & [-1, .4] \\ \hline (-2, .4) & [4, .7] & .6 & 1 & (-1, .4) \\ \hline [-2, .4] & [4, .7] & .6 & 1 & [-1, -.4] \\ \hline [-2, .4] & 1 & (-3, .5) & [-3, .5] & [1, .4] \\ \hline \end{array}$$

$$[\tilde{N}]^4 = \begin{array}{|c|c|c|c|c|} \hline [-2, .4] & 1 & [-3, .5] & [-3, .5] & [-1, -.4] \\ \hline [-2, .4] & 1 & [-3, .5] & [-3, .5] & (-1, .4) \\ \hline (-2, .4) & [-4, .7] & .6 & 1 & [-1, .4] \\ \hline [-2, .4] & [4, .7] & .6 & 1 & [-1, -.4] \\ \hline [-2, .4] & 1 & [-3, .5] & [-3, .5] & (-1, .4) \\ \hline \end{array}$$

We pause: $[\tilde{N}]^* = [\tilde{N}]^4$ and obtain

$$[\hat{N}] = \begin{array}{|c|c|c|c|c|} \hline [-2, .4] & 1 & [-3, .5] & [-3, .5] & [-1, .4] \\ \hline (-2, .4) & 1 & [-3, .5] & [-3, .5] & (-1, .4) \\ \hline [-2, .4] & [4, .7] & .6 & 1 & [-1, .4] \\ \hline [-2, .4] & (-4, .7) & .6 & 1 & [-1, -.4] \\ \hline [-2, .4] & 1 & [-3, .5] & [-3, .5] & [-1, .4] \\ \hline \end{array}$$

In our case of application, let us say the controller arrives on Monday morning, tests the system which is in state 3 and wants to know the possibility of finding the system in state 1 on Wednesday morning since he will then be able to sell shares to obtain money and if it will be convenient for him to plan which investment shares he should sell.

In this way, we have:

$$\begin{array}{c}
 \begin{array}{cccccc}
 & 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 & 5 \\
 \hline
 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\
 2 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\
 3 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\
 4 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\
 5 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0
 \end{array} \\
 [f_0] = \\
 = \begin{array}{ccccc}
 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 & 5 \\
 \hline
 [-2, .4] & [0, .7] & .6 & 1 & M, .4]
 \end{array}
 \end{array}$$

Thus if the initial state of the system is state 3 in a near future moment the maximum conjecture would be found in 4. Nevertheless, concentrating on the established question above, we can observe the possibility of [0.2, 0.4] in state 1 of the system on Wednesday.

It should be pointed out that, utilizing the concept of maximum presumption, the notion of the persistent state does not make sense. In other words, we can not say that the number of times that the system will be in state 1 during a year will be $260 \times [0.2, 0.4] = [52, 104]$. However, it is possible instead of pretending to reach the limited case, to establish the situation in the future after some relatively short stages. If the corresponding matrixes have a reduced number of states, these calculations can be of real significance while in the contrary case we would need the intervention of a crystal ball.

IV. Summary

This paper studies the different proposals interested in facilitating the aim of two principle objectives in cash management decision-making: the fixing of the optimum level of liquidity and the determination of the period and amount of the transactions between the funds and the portfolio of shares. Nevertheless, in our study we have occupied ourselves primarily with the second objective stated above. Thus, we have analyzed the utility presented by the application of the Markov chains when considering cash flows as a random variable.

Nevertheless, there are situations in which it is not possible to use probabilities, as when there is uncertainty instead of aleatoriness: if our knowledge of the environment is imprecise, as happens in fuzzy cash management control, the model must include the notion of chains with fuzzy data instead of probabilities recently developed by Professors Kaufmann and Gil Aluja. This way in our paper we have examined the utility presented by the "fuzzy chains of Kaufmann and Gil Aluja", where the chains are made by means of operators associated with maximum-minimums (the most proper decision) while the Markov chains are carried out by means of operators associated with sum-products (the one who decides considers himself objective and always the most objective).

V. References

- BACHILLER CACHO, A. et al.: 'Gestión económico-financiera del circulante'. Pirámide. Madrid, 1982.
- BAUMOL, W.J.: "The Transactions Demand for Cash: An Inventory Theoretic Approach". The Quarterly Journal of Economics. Vol. 66, N° 4. November 1952, pp. 545-556.
- BERANEK, W.: "Análisis para la toma de decisiones financieras". Labor. Barcelona, 1975.
- CAÑIBANO CALVO, L. y BUENO CAMPOS, E.: "Autofinanciación y tesorería en la empresa: el cash-flow". Pirámide. Madrid, 1983.
- CHAÑAS, S. and KOLODZIEJYK, W.: "Maximun flow in a network with fuzzy arc capacities". Fuzzy Sets & Systems. Vol. 8, N° 2, August 1982, pp. 165-174.
- CZOGALA, E. and ZIMMERMANN, H.J.: "The aggregation operations for decision-making in probabilistic fuzzy environment". Fuzzy Sets & Systems. Vol. 13, N° 3, August 1984, pp. 223-240.
- DELGADO, M. et al.: "Some structural and optimization problems on fuzzy graphs". In KULIKOWSKI, R. and RUDNICKI, J. (eds.): "System Analysis and Computer Science". Omnitech Press. Poland, 1990, pp. 47-63.
- FEDRIZZI, M. et. al. (eds.): "Interactive Fuzzy Optimization". Springer-Verlag. Berlin, 1991.
- GIL ALUJA, J.: "El estudio dinámico de la elección de inversiones". Técnica Contable, Febrero 1967, págs. 41-50 y 66.
- GIL LAFUENTE, A.M.: "El análisis financiero en la incertidumbre". Ariel. Barcelona, 1990.
- GREGORY, G.: "Cash flow Models: A Review". OMEGA. Vol. 4, N° 6, 1976, pp. 643-656.
- ITAKURA, H. and NISHIKAWA, Y.: "Fuzzy network technique for technological forecasting". Fuzzy Sets & Systems. Vol 14, N° 2, November 1984, pp. 99-114.
- KAUFMANN, A.: "Métodos y Modelos de la programación matemática". CECSA. México, 1966.
- KAUFMANN, A. y GIL ALUJA, J.: "Introducción de la teoría de los subconjuntos borrosos a la gestión de las empresas". Milladoiro. Santiago de Compostela, 1986.
- KAUFMANN, A. y GIL ALUJA, J.: "Técnicas operativas de gestión para el tratamiento de la incertidumbre". Hispano Europea. Barcelona, 1987.
- KAUFMANN, A. y GIL ALUJA, J.: "Modelos para la investigación de efectos olvidados". Milladoiro. Santiago de Compostela, 1988.
- KAUFMANN, A. y GIL ALUJA, J.: "Las matemáticas del azar y de la incertidumbre". Centro de Estudios Ramón Ateces. Madrid, 1990.
- KAUFMANN, A. y GIL ALUJA, J.: "Nuevas técnicas para la dirección estratégica". Universidad de Barcelona. Barcelona, 1991.
- MILLER, H. and ORR, A.: "A Model of the Demand for Money by Firms". The Quarterly Journal of Economics. Vol. 80, N° 3. August 1966, pp. 413-435.
- PATINKIN, D.: "Money, Interest and Prices". Row, Peterson & Co. Evanston, 1956.
- ZIMMERMANN, H.J.: "Using fuzzy sets in operations research". European Journal of Operations Research, Vol. 13. N° 3. 1983, pp. 201-216.

An Analysis of Chaos Deactivation in Fuzzy System Networks Using Incomplete Fuzzy Logic System?

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Abstract

The results reported in [1], (2), (3) on chaos in fussy systems, in (4) on the analysis of complete and incomplete fussy logic controllers and in [5] on case studies of chaotic fussy systems, are applied in this paper to fussy system networks. The method of chaos deactivation, as presented in (5), is adapted to the specific aspects of the fussy system networks.

Introduction

In this paper, a fussy logic system is named complete (from the linguistic point of view), if for every linguistic degree of the fussy system input(s) there is at least one fussy rule with the respective linguistic degree in the antecedent. A fussy logic system is named incomplete when some of the input(s) linguistic degrees there are not in any fussy rules of the system. An incompletely described fussy logic system covers the Kucldian input domain (i.e. it is a complete system) only if the bases of two successive input membership functions have common points (the intersection of their supports is not the empty set). Further details on this subject can be found in (4 J).

Turning a complete fuzzy system that exhibits chaos into an incomplete one, by eliminating some rules, can stabilize the behavior. This method is easy to implement, because it involves only the elimination of rules. This condition is equivalent to create a region in the crisp input space, for which the crisp input value settles only one input fuzzy value.

The block diagram of the fuzzy system network with two fuzzy system is shown in Figure 1. Here, the symbols $In(1,1)$, $In(1,2)$ and $Out(i)$ stand for the inputs and output of the first fuzzy system respectively, and the symbols $In(2,1)$, $In(2,2)$ and $Out(2)$ stand for the inputs and output of the second fuzzy system, respectively.

The a_1 , b_1 coefficients stand for the parameters of the crisp feedback of the first fuzzy system, the a_2 , b_2 coefficients stand for the crisp